

Agenda for Future Research

In the fields of:

- **Transformative Behavioural Change for Energy Communities**
- **Environmental Sustainability in Micro-Entrepreneurship**

The ACCTING project explores the impact of Green Deal policies on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate and mitigate potential negative effects.

Its Agenda for Future Research highlights key research gaps across Green Deal policy areas and provides a clear overview of research priorities and needs for a fair and sustainable transition. By doing so, it aims to contribute to the development of future research agendas and pave the way for inclusive and effective policymaking and implementation.

The full set of research agendas covering other thematic areas can be found [on the ACCTING project website](#).

Theme: Transformative Behavioural Change for Energy and Solidarity Communities

This research theme explores how energy communities that wish to pursue also societal goals (so called: Energy and Solidarity Communities or inclusive energy communities) can serve as catalysts for sustainable practices and social inclusion, focusing on the transformative behavioural changes needed to achieve equitable and environmentally conscious outcomes. It examines the dynamics of individual and collective behaviour, the barriers and enablers to participation among people who experiment disadvantageous conditions, and the structural and policy frameworks required to support inclusive and scalable energy solutions. By addressing these dimensions, the theme seeks to identify actionable pathways for supporting resilient and socially equitable energy transitions.

ACCTING Findings

- People in disadvantageous conditions had often limited prior knowledge of sustainability practices, which impacted their engagement. However, targeted workshops and meetings improved participation rates and fostered a sense of community.
- Direct support and active communication may enhance vulnerable individuals' inclusion. Trust in project leaders was a crucial factor for involvement, particularly in projects targeting energy poverty.
- Intersectionality emerges as a key factor, with women and individuals from minority backgrounds facing distinct challenges and opportunities within energy communities.
- Behavioural adaptation was often driven by economic necessity rather than environmental awareness, where residents reduced energy usage to cut costs.
- Social interactions and communal activities may be effective in teaching sustainability practices and fostering pro-environmental behaviour.
- Educational efforts and participatory governance can sustain long-term behavioural change among members.
- Municipal and organisational support plays a critical role in project success, but unclear national policies on energy communities hinder broader scalability.

- Financial challenges, such as the lack of subsidised programmes for vulnerable groups, were a recurring issue across case studies.
- Local leadership and dedicated governance are important in overcoming structural barriers and engaging people in disadvantageous conditions.

Research gaps and directions for future research

Subtheme 1. Social Inclusion in Energy Communities

Energy and solidarity communities are increasingly recognised for their potential to alleviate energy poverty and foster sustainable development, yet their capacity to include marginalised groups remains uneven. Low-income families, and immigrants often face systemic barriers (such as language constraints, cultural isolation, and limited social capital) that hinder full participation in community energy initiatives. Moreover, a lack of trust in local governance or project coordinators may exacerbate these exclusions, particularly where historically underserved populations perceive initiatives as elitist or inaccessible. Even when technical solutions and financial support mechanisms are available, meaningful engagement can be undermined by inadequate outreach and the absence of culturally sensitive communication strategies. These challenges point to the urgent need for more comprehensive, bottom-up approaches that address intersectional vulnerabilities and ensure that energy and solidarity communities truly embody principles of equity and empowerment.

Research questions

Contextual and Cultural Barriers

- How do social and cultural contexts influence the participation of people in disadvantageous conditions in energy communities?
- What mechanisms ensure equitable involvement of people in disadvantageous conditions, such as single-parent households and immigrants, in energy community projects?

Trust-Building Strategies

- How does trust impact long-term participation and commitment in energy communities?
- What are the critical trust-building factors between energy community leaders, policymakers, and vulnerable groups?

Intersectionality and Gender

- How can gender+ intersectional approaches can reshape participation dynamics in energy communities?
- What specific outreach and engagement strategies can address the unique barriers faced by women, migrants, and other intersectionally vulnerable groups?

Incentives facilitating the engagement of people in disadvantageous conditions

- What kind of incentives (financial subsidies, capacity-building programs, easing of regulatory requirements) can most effectively facilitate the participation of people in disadvantageous conditions in energy communities?
- How can public and private funding, including corporate social responsibility (CSR) and impact investment, be harnessed to subsidise membership and initial costs for those most in need?

Leveraging Existing Community Schemes

- Can energy and solidarity communities be built using other already successful local community structures (e.g., housing cooperatives, local cultural or sports clubs)?
- How can these existing networks accelerate trust, reduce administrative hurdles, and promote knowledge-sharing for sustainable energy practices?

Subtheme 2. Behavioural Adaptation and Sustainability Practices

Despite various initiatives aimed at encouraging pro-environmental habits, long-term adoption of such practices among energy community members remains limited and sometimes inconsistent. Although financial incentives and technological support can generate initial uptake, the deeper dynamics of knowledge transfer, social cohesion, and lived experiences are under-examined. Community-led workshops and peer-learning forums can foster a collective identity, yet their sustained impact depends on how well new behaviours align with everyday routines, cultural norms, and individuals' sense of agency. To address these gaps, longitudinal research that captures not just the early success of sustainability programmes but also the evolving relationships, power dynamics, and personal narratives is necessary for understanding how pro-environmental actions can become deeply rooted.

Research questions

Scalability and Inclusivity

- How can successful community-based energy models be scaled while maintaining inclusivity and equitable benefits?
- What role does peer learning and cross-community exchange play in promoting scalable solutions?

Sustaining Engagement Over Time

- How do energy communities sustain inclusivity and engagement across diverse member profiles over time?
- Can the example of energy and solidarity communities act as a catalyst for wider environmental agency of vulnerable groups (e.g., spillover of pro-environmental behaviours into other social or environmental fields)?

Communication and Outreach

- What are the most effective messaging strategies to resonate with economically constrained individuals and underscore both financial and environmental benefits?
- How do local leaders and champions shape narratives around green transitions that motivate long-term behavioural change rather than short-term cost savings alone?

Subtheme 3. Policy and Structural Drivers of Behavioural Change

Recent scholarship on energy communities has emphasised their potential to democratise clean energy and alleviate energy poverty. Nonetheless, policy frameworks commonly lack explicit requirements or incentives to ensure that disadvantaged and low-income groups can participate. In many regions, government guidelines fail to define eligibility criteria, participation quotas, or decision-making processes that prioritise marginalised populations, leaving also the communities that at least formally pursue societal goals at risk of exclusion of disadvantaged people. Insufficient information on cost-sharing arrangements, along with complex administrative processes, reduces the ease of participation for individuals lacking initial resources or technical proficiency. Thus, instead of mitigating inequalities, current regulatory frameworks may reinforce them by privileging individuals with the resources and knowledge to navigate bureaucratic obstacles and obtain financial support, thereby undermining the equity aims that energy communities are allegedly meant to serve.

Research questions

Effective Policy Frameworks

- What policy frameworks are most effective in promoting the inclusion of people in disadvantageous conditions in energy and solidarity communities?
- How can local governance structures and financial incentives be optimised to support energy and solidarity community scalability?

Municipal and Administrative Support

- What role do municipal policies play in reducing the bureaucratic and financial barriers to the establishment of energy communities?
- How can local policymakers embark on a deliberative process that genuinely engages people in disadvantageous conditions, and what are the boundaries of resilience in this context?

Private Sector Engagement and CSR

- How can private-sector key players (e.g., banks, energy production/distribution companies) facilitate the inclusion of people in disadvantageous conditions, in energy communities and so, facilitate their evolution towards energy and solidarity communities?
- Can this engagement be integrated within their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Impactful Investment schemes to ensure long-term support?

Public-Private Partnerships

- Can the financial burden of inclusive energy communities be met through the involvement of private actors such as energy companies and commercial renewable energy developers?
- What are the best governance models (public, private, or hybrid) to ensure transparency, accountability, and equitable cost-sharing?

Technology Accessibility and Circular Approaches

- How can technologies (e.g., photovoltaic panels, smart meters) be made more affordable and accessible to energy communities while responding to their specific needs?
- What role could recycling, reusing, or the “maker/DIY” movement play in lowering barriers to entry and fostering local innovation in green energy transitions?

Theme: Bridging Environmental Sustainability and Social Inclusion in Vulnerable Micro-Entrepreneurship

This theme addresses the integration of social and environmental objectives for micro-entrepreneurs who operate under resource constraints. It explores the systemic, behavioural, and policy factors that can enable or hinder the transition to sustainable practices, focusing particularly on vulnerable groups such as migrants, low-income entrepreneurs, and women-led enterprises.

ACCTING Findings

- Across the 21 ACCTING case studies, entrepreneurs frequently cited difficulties in securing financial support for sustainability measures, such as energy-efficient equipment and renewable energy solutions.
- Informal enterprises, particularly in Belgium and Norway, lacked access to formal financial systems, further exacerbating their vulnerabilities.
- Entrepreneurs in Greece and Romania showed interest in adopting sustainable practices but lacked technical knowledge and understanding of available incentives. Peer learning and brainstorming sessions, as facilitated by the ACCTING project, proved effective in introducing practical solutions to micro-entrepreneurs.
- Resilience to financial and policy shocks varied among the cases, with enterprises in Romania demonstrating higher adaptability through integrated sustainability approaches.
- Entrepreneurs in Belgium and Norway highlighted difficulties in expanding their operations while maintaining sustainability due to high costs and fragmented support systems.

Research gaps and directions for future research

Subtheme 1. Overcoming Structural Barriers

Micro-entrepreneurs in unstable circumstances frequently struggle with structural limitations that hinder their capacity to implement sustainable practices. These systemic barriers include insufficient capital reserves and financial flows, lack of qualified human resources, heightened risk perceptions, and fragmented support networks, which collectively limit both the exploration and implementation of green innovations. Even when opportunities for environmental retrofitting or adoption of renewable energy technologies arise, the lack of assets, high interest rates, and lack of information and support from competent people restrict their access to formal credit and knowledge resources. In many cases, these entrepreneurs must prioritise immediate financial viability over medium/longer-term environmental investments, so creating a loop in which resource limitations hinder the development or expansion of sustainable business models. As a result, the potential for micro-enterprises to drive local sustainability transitions remains underrealised, underscoring the need for integrated policy support to help vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs bridge systemic gaps and progress toward environmentally resilient operations.

Research questions

Intersection of Environmental Investments and Socio-Economic Constraints

- How do environmental investments intersect with socio-economic constraints, and what adaptive strategies can enable micro-enterprises to optimise both sustainability and resilience?

Transformative Policy Frameworks

- What transformative policy frameworks and mechanisms can be designed to address the intersectional needs of micro-enterprises operating within resource-constrained environments?

Alignment with Lived Realities

- To what extent do existing support systems (e.g., incentives, subsidies, and training) align with the lived realities of vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs, and how can these systems be reimagined to foster equitable green transitions?

Institutions and Intermediaries

- Which institutions (e.g., local chambers of commerce, ESCOs, larger enterprises in their same value-chain, NGOs, cooperative banks, and municipal agencies) can act as facilitators or intermediary organisations for the green energy transition of micro-enterprises?
- How can networks among SMEs facilitate the green energy transition of micro-enterprises?
- How can local policymakers create administrative arrangements that ease access to credit, training, and mentorship for vulnerable entrepreneurs?

Subtheme 2. Behavioural Spillovers and Network Dynamics in Micro-Entrepreneurial Ecosystems

The adoption of sustainable practices by micro-enterprises can yield critical spillover effects among broader stakeholder networks, yet limited knowledge exists regarding how these changes diffuse across interconnected economic and social structures. Because micro-enterprises are sometimes (far from ever) deeply integrated with local ecosystems of employees, suppliers, and customers, shifts toward resource-efficient production and low-carbon solutions have the potential to generate further modifications in operating routines, procurement patterns, and consumption norms. However, emerging evidence suggests that distinct network characteristics (particularly trust-based ties, supportive policy environments, and shared learning platforms) can significantly determine whether initial steps toward sustainability foster deeper transformative change or remain isolated to a few early adopters. Adopting a multi-level perspective that accounts for the interplay of cultural, organisational, and market factors is thus crucial for tracing the ripple effects of green behaviours and designing interventions that amplify positive outcomes. Without such integrated analysis, policy measures risk overlooking the subtle ways in which micro-enterprise ecosystems shape, and are simultaneously shaped by, evolving sustainability practices.

Research questions

Spillover Effects

- How do sustainability behaviours adopted by micro-entrepreneurs trigger adaptive responses among employees, suppliers, and customers?

Experimental Interventions

- What experimental interventions (e.g., nudges, peer-learning initiatives) can amplify positive behavioural spillovers across ecosystems?

Trust and Reciprocity

- How do micro-entrepreneurs' perceptions of trust and reciprocity shape their willingness to engage in sustainability-oriented networks?
- What digital and non-digital platforms can be designed to facilitate inclusive and trust-based collaborations for sustainability?

Messaging and Conflict Resolution

- How to overcome conflicting views on "traditional energy usage" and build trust in the green transition among micro-enterprises with limited human and financial resources?
- What are the most effective messages or signals to society that can legitimise and support vulnerable entrepreneurs' green transition efforts?

Subtheme 3. Enhancing Resilience and Scalability

Vulnerable micro-enterprises, often operating with limited financial reserves and restricted access to supportive networks, frequently encounter substantial obstacles in maintaining environmentally responsible practices over time. External shocks, such as economic recessions, pandemics, or fluctuating policy incentives, can worsen the vulnerability of these ventures, forcing owners to redirect scarce capital away from sustainability measures. Even when these enterprises manage to adopt more sustainable processes, such as installing energy-efficient technologies or integrating circular economy principles, the lack of supportive institutional frameworks and fragmented policy incentives makes it difficult to scale these practices effectively. Moreover, stakeholders in local ecosystems (suppliers, financial institutions, and municipal agencies) may be uncoordinated, further hindering access to sustained technical or financial assistance.

Without robust capacity-building programmes, micro-grants, and targeted mentorship schemes, these ventures are vulnerable to reverting to previous traditional practices once the initial drive for sustainability diminishes. Furthermore, uncertainty around consumer demand for green products or services can dissuade entrepreneurs from committing resources to environmental improvements that may not yield immediate returns. This cyclical pattern underscores the need for comprehensive policy interventions, including public-private partnerships and participatory governance models, that buffer against market fluctuations and enable micro-enterprises to retain a commitment to green transitions. Conversely, through integrated support structures (i.e. a supportive institutional framework including local chambers of commerce, ESCOs, larger enterprises in their same value-chain, NGOs, cooperative banks, and municipal agencies) micro-entrepreneurs can more effectively mitigate risks, foster innovation, and ultimately build resilience against economic and ecological uncertainties.

Research questions

Resilience under Constraints

- What factors contribute to the resilience of micro-enterprises in sustaining and advancing sustainable practices against resource constraints and external shocks?

Policy Mechanisms and Partnerships

- What novel policy mechanisms, including public-private partnerships and adaptive governance models, can ensure long-term support, scalability, and innovation for environmentally sustainable micro-enterprises?

Empowering Entrepreneurs

- How can micro-entrepreneurs (especially from vulnerable populations) be empowered to set up realistic, stepwise, and resilient plans for green transitions?
- How can training programmes, mentorship, and collaborative platforms help entrepreneurs balance immediate financial needs with long-term sustainability goals?

Cross-Cutting Considerations

Complexity of Intersectional Vulnerabilities

Intersectional vulnerabilities refer to the overlapping social, economic, and cultural disadvantages that individuals face due to multiple intersecting identities. These layers of marginalisation compound one another, creating unique forms of exclusion or hardship that a single-axis approach (e.g., focusing on gender alone) often fails to capture.

In the context of sustainability transitions, this means that a low-income, immigrant woman entrepreneur, for example, may experience not just the constraints of insufficient financial resources but also language barriers, discrimination, and limited social networks, all of which undermine her ability to adopt or benefit from green solutions. These compounded vulnerabilities reduce access to credit, training, and policy support, making it harder to invest in sustainable technologies or practices. Moreover, many existing sustainability frameworks or policy instruments fail to account for the interplay of socio-cultural factors that shape people's willingness and capacity to engage.

As a result, minimal understanding exists of how these overlapping identities interact to produce challenges that are more than the sum of their parts. Empirical research rarely disaggregates data to recognise and address specific layers of marginalisation. Consequently, well-intentioned initiatives risk reinforcing or exacerbating inequalities by overlooking the barriers that intersectionally vulnerable groups face. To build truly inclusive pathways toward environmental sustainability, future research and policy must better capture the lived realities of people experiencing multifaceted disadvantages, ensuring that strategies account for the full complexity of intersectional vulnerability.

Research questions

Mapping Overlapping Vulnerabilities

- How do overlapping vulnerabilities (e.g., disability, migrant status, and gender) amplify barriers in transition to Green Deal?
- How can these complex challenges be systematically mapped and addressed?

Converging top-down and bottom-up

- What enabling conditions allow top-down policies and bottom-up resilience strategies to converge, ensuring that local participatory processes (enriched by gender-sensitive planning, private-sector CSR programmes, and robust support for vulnerable groups) collectively advance broader "Green Deal" objectives for an inclusive green transition?

About ACCTING

ACCTING is an EU-funded project aiming to understand the impact of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups, prevent inequalities, and produce knowledge and innovations to advance behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

As the project approaches its conclusion in May 2025, the research team has developed a Research Agenda outlining key knowledge gaps across Green Deal policy areas. This document serves as a valuable reference for future research and policymaking.

Discover the [Research Agenda published during the first research cycle](#).

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Contact us: accting-eu@esf.org

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